

Thermodynamics of excess binding of inorganic salts and organic solutes to crab hemocyanin

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Abstract : Using isopiestic vapor pressure technique, extents of water bound to complex metalloprotein hemocyanin obtained from crab have been determined in the absence and presence of inorganic salts, sucrose and urea at a fixed temperature. The water vapor adsorption curve for hemocyanin in the range of water activity varying between zero to unity is type III BET isotherm. Moles of water absorbed per kg of hemocyanin at unit water activity a_1 have been evaluated by extrapolation method and the results support several models of bound water for different ranges of a_1 . The standard free energies of adsorption ΔG^0 for water-protein interaction at different temperatures have been calculated using Bull equation in integrated form. Based on Clausius-Clapeyron equation in integrated form, the integral enthalpy for water-hemocyanin interaction has also been evaluated. Using the isopiestic technique, values of excess binding of solute Γ_2^1 and Γ_1^2 excess binding of solvent per kg of hemocyanin in the presence of different bulk mole-fractions X_2 of solutes (LiCl, NaCl, KCl, NaBr, NaI, KSCN, urea, and sucrose) have been calculated in each case from the evaluated values of the Gibbs surface excess. In certain ranges of solute concentration, the plot of $\Gamma_1^2.X_2$ vs X_1 becomes linear so that moles of water and solute bound per kg of hemocyanin respectively can be calculated. X_1 and X_2 stand for the mole-fraction of the solvent and solute in the bulk phase of the sample. Also, using integrated form of the Gibbs adsorption equation, standard free energy change (ΔG^0) for the solute-hemocyanin and the solvent-hemocyanin interactions for different systems have been computed and the values have been compared critically.

Keywords : Isopiestic vapor pressure techniques, hydration of crab hemocyanin, Gibbs surface excess of solutes, solvent bound to hemocyanin.

Introduction

Hemocyanin is a copper-containing respiratory protein of numerous mollusks and arthropods. It resembles hemerythrin in the lack of porphyrins or any other prosthetic group. It does not occur in blood cells but is present in a soluble form in the hemolymph of the animals. It combines with oxygen to form a blue oxygenated compound which contains one molecule of oxygen for two copper atoms¹. Hemocyanin of many arthropods contain 0.17–0.18% copper². The valence state of copper is not yet clear whether it is in the cupric or cuprous state. It has been suggested that copper atoms are bound to sul-

phur atoms of cysteine residues. The determination of molecular weight of hemocyanin, by several methods like sedimentation technique with ultracentrifuge, osmometry and the light-scattering gives values varying from 5.0×10^6 to 1.0×10^7 . Hemocyanin from the crab, *limulus polyphemus*, is found to consist of almost spherical particle with an average diameter 200 Å, in which six subunits are joined together³. Structure of hemocyanin and its subunits have been discussed extensively in a recent review by Decker *et al.*⁴. There are several domains in this protein having helical, bundle and copper unit⁴.

Recently binding of water and various types of solutes

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to many types of proteins (including metal containing protein hemoglobin) have been extensively studied using isopiestic method of vapor pressure measurement. So far measurement of hydration of hemocyanin has not been studied by this method. Such study followed by thermodynamic analysis will be presented in this paper.

From the information cited above for hemocyanin, it comes out that the model study of the interaction of hemocyanin with electrolytes and non-electrolytes in the aqueous environment may be of great importance from the biological point of view. The role of water in controlling the protein-water interaction in the presence and absence of various inorganic and organic solutes has been examined using thermodynamic analysis of the data for binding interaction occurring in crab hemocyanin system.

Materials and method :

Hemocyanin isolated from the horseshoe crab, limulus polyphemus was obtained from the laboratory of Professor R. Bhadra, one of the author, Indian Institute of Chemical Biology, Kolkata. It was dried in a desiccator containing concentrated H_2SO_4 , for 4–5 days and preserved in the refrigerator keeping in another desiccator containing anhydrous $CaCl_2$. The electrolytes LiCl, NaCl, KCl, CsCl, KBr, KI, Na_2SO_4 , $CaCl_2$ and non-electrolytes sucrose (all analytical grade) were used directly without any further purification. Urea was twice recrystallized out from warm ethanol. Double distilled water was used throughout the investigation.

For the hydration measurement of dried hemocyanin following isotopic method of Bull and coworkers^{9–11} was employed. Definite volumes (100 ml) of sulphuric acid solutions of different concentrations (ranging from about 0.5 N to 31 N) were taken in specially designed desiccators (Fig. 1). These solutions are termed as ‘reference solutions’. Definite amounts (approx. 0.2 g) of dry hemocyanin were taken in specially designed dry weighing bottles with their lids open (vide Fig. 1) and these were allowed to float in the magnetically stirred reference solutions taken in the desiccators attached by means of tripod stands. The desiccators were then closed, evacuated appropriately and kept in air-thermostat for 7 days at 22 °C, 30 °C and 37 °C so that the exchange of water vapor between hemocyanin in a sample bottle and magnetically stirred reference solution would take place at each temperature. This ultimately leads to the attainment

Fig. 1. Outline of isopiestic experiment for protein hydration.

of isopiestic equilibrium. The desiccators in each temperature were opened carefully and weights of the weighing bottles were taken. The concentration of H_2SO_4 in the reference solution of isopiestic equilibrium (with sample in each case was estimated from which the relative humidity P/P_0 was known using standard reference tables^{9–11}).

From the difference in initial and final weights of the sample bottle, moles n_1 of water vapour adsorbed per kilogram of hemocyanin in sample bottle were calculated at 22 °C, 30 °C and 37 °C respectively (vide Table 1).

For the determination of hydration of protein in the presence of neutral salts, sucrose and urea^{6,10,11} respectively, a definite amount of dry hemocyanin along with a definite amount of dry solute (salt, sucrose or urea) were taken in the sample bottle as before and this was floated on the stirred reference solution of the same solute in the desiccator, so that the system attained isopiestic equilibrium within 7 days. Each sample bottle was then taken out from the desiccator and weighed accurately. From the difference between final and initial weights of the sample bottle, total moles of water n_1^t in the sample bottle at final state of isopiestic equilibrium was obtained.

Table 1. Values of Δn_1^0 and $(-\Delta G_w^0)$ for the hydration of hemocyanin in absence of solute

Temperature (K)	Δn_1^0 (Moles/kg of hemocyanin)	$-\Delta G_w^0$ (kJ/kg of hemocyanin)
295.0	45.0	29.0
303.0	53.0	38.0
310.0	65.0	45.0

Total moles (n_2^t) of salt, sucrose or urea in the sample were initially known in the sample so that molality (m_2^t) of solute component 2 before interaction with water and salt with hemocyanin was known. The molality (m_2) of the solute in the reference solution at isopiestic equilibrium had been estimated by direct weighing of solute obtained from a definite weight of the reference solution taken in a weighing bottle after complete drying at 105 °C. For LiCl, CaCl₂ and urea, this type of heating may decompose solute. An indirect method^{10,12} was used for estimation of m_2 of these solutes in the reference solution at isopiestic equilibrium.

Values of excess moles Γ_2^1 of solute component 2 sorbed or bound in excess per kg of hemocyanin can be calculated using eq. (1)^{11,12},

$$\Gamma_2^1 = \frac{n_1^t M_1}{1000} (m_2^t - m_2) \quad (1)$$

Here $n_1^t M_1$ is equal to W_1 total amount of water component in kg 1 per kg of hemocyanin in the sample bottle at isopiestic equilibrium. M_1 stands for molecular weight of solvent. Values of m_2^t and m_2 can be obtained directly from experiments. The molality m_2 of the reference solution experimentally determined at isopiestic equilibrium may be taken as the molality of the solute in the sample provided that the contribution of the sample to the water vapour in presence of high concentration of solute is negligible.

Values of Γ_2^1 becomes positive when $m_2^t > m_2$ and negative when $m_2^t < m_2$. Replacing m_2^t and m_2 in eq. (1) by $1000 n_2^t / M_1 n_1^t$ and $1000 n_2 / M_1 n_1$, respectively one finds¹⁶⁻¹⁸,

$$\Gamma_2^1 = n_2^t - n_1^t \left(\frac{n_2}{n_1} \right) \quad (2)$$

and

$$-\Gamma_2^1 \left(\frac{n_1}{n_2} \right) = n_1^t - n_2^t \left(\frac{n_1}{n_2} \right) = \Gamma_1^2 \quad (3)$$

Here n_1 and n_2 stand for the number of moles of free solvent and solute molecules respectively present with one kg of protein in sample at isopiestic equilibrium. Γ_2^1 and Γ_1^2 stand for relative excesses of solute and solvent respectively whose values can directly be evaluated from

measured values of n_1^t , n_2^t and m_2 since

$$\frac{n_2}{n_1} = \frac{X_2}{X_1} = \frac{m_2}{55.5} \quad (4)$$

Here X_1 and X_2 stand for mole fractions of the solvent and solute respectively in the sample system.

Results and discussion

In Fig. 2, moles of water vapour (n_1) bound per kg of hemocyanin at 22 °C, 30 °C and 37 °C were plotted against relative vapour pressure of water (P/P_0) or water activity (a_1) (also known as relative humidity according to Raoult's law), within the total range of a_1 varying between zero to unity. The isotherms are sigmoidal in shape and similar in form to that expected from the type III BET eq. (13). The isotherms in this figure may quali-

Fig. 2. Plot of n_1 , moles of water bound per kg of hemocyanin versus a_1 , water activity. (Δ) : 22 °C, (\circ) : 30 °C, (\bullet) : 37 °C.

tatively be divided into three parts. First part of the isotherm in the range of relative humidity zero to 0.20 is for the formation of primary layer of water at the protein surface¹⁹. In this region, water molecules are bound strongly to the hydrophilic groups of protein thus forming a monolayer of water. The second part of the curve for relative humidity ranging between 0.20 to 0.75 is responsible for the swelling of protein. Beyond 0.75 relative humidity, adsorption, however, increases significantly which indicates the formation of multilayers of adsorbate molecules¹⁸⁻²⁰. The extrapolated value of n_1 at a_1 equal

to unity corresponds to the maximum and effective amount in moles of water bound by kg of protein and it is referred to as Δn_1^0 . Values of Δn_1^0 for the binding of water to hemocyanin are found to be 45.0, 53.0 and 65.0 moles per kg of protein respectively at 22 °C, 30 °C and 37 °C, which are included in Table 1. The activity of the water adsorbed by the protein sample must be less than unity, since this bound water may remain in equilibrium with water vapor of relative pressure less than unity. In other words, the escaping tendency of the adsorbed water to the vapor state is always less than that of pure water in the absence of protein. This tendency may be relatively compared with each other by the activity gradient $\left(\frac{da_1}{dn_1}\right)$, obtained from the slope of a_1 versus n_1 plot⁶. When n_1 is close to zero, this gradient also tends to become zero. As n_1 increases, the value of this gradient at first increases and attains a maximum value and finally it reduces to extremely low values when values of n_1 are extrapolated to 45.0, 53.0 and 65.0 moles of water adsorbed per kg of hemocyanin at 22 °C, 30 °C and 37 °C respectively. By this extrapolation method it was observed by Chatteraj and Mitra¹² that the values of Δn_1^0 are 26.5, 23.5 and 26.6 moles per kg of serum albumin, hemoglobin and egg albumin respectively at 25 °C. These values of Δn_1^0 may be regarded as the maximum and the effective amount of water to be accommodated within the bound phase of protein-water system, thus completing various hydration shells. Any value of n_1 between zero to these extrapolated values may be termed as bound water (Δn_1^0). It may be further noted that the value of n_1 in excess of the extrapolated value (close to 0.99 to 1.00 water activity) corresponds to insignificant activity gradient so that it may be regarded as free water in contact with hydrated protein. At a_1 exactly equal to unity, large amount of free water could be transferred to sample bottle so that hydrated protein solutions may be imagined to be infinitely dilute at isopiestic equilibrium. This stage of an infinitely dilute protein solution may be regarded as the standard state of unit water activity in reference to which the values of activity and other thermodynamic properties may be expressed suitably.

From Fig. 2 it may be further noted that the value of n_1 at a given value of a_1 increases with the increase of temperature. It signifies that, with the increase of tem-

perature, more water molecules are bound to newly exposed sites of the protein as a result of hydrophobic effect.

The integral free energy change (ΔG_w^0) due to the hydration of protein at activities lower than unity can be evaluated from eq. (5)⁶.

$$\Delta G_w^0 = -RT \int_{a_1=0}^{a_1=1} \left(\frac{n_1}{a_1}\right) da_1 \quad (5)$$

From the graphical evaluation of the area under the curve obtained by plotting $\left(\frac{n_1}{a_1}\right)$ as a function of a_1 between the limit $a_1 = 0$ to $a_1 = 1$, the value of the integral may be calculated. The value of ΔG_w^0 , according to eq. (5) is always negative. The values of ΔG_w^0 for the hydration of hemocyanin were found to be -29.0, -38.0 and -45.0 kJ/kg at 22 °C, 30 °C and 37 °C respectively (vide Table 1). At 27 °C, values of ΔG_w^0 for the hydration BSA, hemoglobin, egg albumin and myosin reported by Chatteraj *et al.*⁶ are -51.5, -39.4, -40.3 and -30.6 kJ per kg of protein respectively. So like all other proteins, the hydration of hemocyanin is thus a thermodynamically spontaneous process.

The average standard free energy changes $(\Delta G_w^0)_{av}$ for the hydration of hemocyanin were calculated at two different average temperatures.

The integral enthalpy change (ΔH_w^0) of hydration of hemocyanin have been calculated using the integrated form of the Clausius-Clapeyron eq. (6),

$$\Delta H_w^0 = \frac{RT_1 T_2}{T_2 - T_1} \int_0^{\Delta n_1^0} \ln \frac{a_2}{a_1} dn_1 \quad (6)$$

Here a_1 and a_2 are water activities of protein at temperatures T_1 and T_2 respectively. Average values of ΔH_w^0 obtained by using experimental data in eq. (6) are found to be -301.0 and 415 kJ/kg respectively (vide Table 2) at average temperatures 299.0 and 306.5 K.

The average value of ΔS_w^0 equal $\frac{1}{T_{av}} (\Delta H_w^0 - \Delta G_w^0)$ is thus found to be 1.11 and 1.00 kJ kg⁻¹ K respectively (vide Table 2). One finds that magnitudes of ΔH_w^0 and $T_{av} \Delta S_w^0$ are comparable to each other. Thus interaction of hemocyanin with water in the absence of other solutes

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters for the hydration of hemocyanin in absence of solute

Average temperature	$-(\Delta G_w^0)_{av}$ (kJ/kg)	$(\Delta H_w^0)_{av}$ $\times 10^{-2}$ (kJ/kg)	$T_{av}(\Delta S_w^0)_{av}$ $\times 10^{-2}$ (kJ/kg)	$(\Delta S_w^0)_{av}$ kJ kg^{-10} K^{-1}
T_{av} (K)		(kJ/kg)	(kJ/kg)	
299.0	33.5	3.01	3.34	1.11
306.5	41.5	2.68	3.09	1.00

is controlled both by entropy and enthalpy.

We shall now analyse our experimental data on the hydration of hemocyanin in the presence of inorganic salts, urea and sugar in the light of measured values of Γ_2^1 and Γ_1^2 according to eqs. (2) and (3) for excess binding of salt and water to hemocyanin.

If Δn_1 and Δn_2 are the respective numbers of moles of water and solute bound in absolute amounts per kg of the protein in sample bottle, then n_2^{\ddagger} is equal to $n_2 + \Delta n_2$ and

n_1^{\ddagger} is equal to $n_1 + \Delta n_1$. Also according to eq. (4), $\left(\frac{n_2}{n_1}\right)$

is equal to $\left(\frac{X_2}{X_1}\right)$, the eqs. (2) and (3) may be transformed as

$$\Gamma_2^1 = \Delta n_2 - \Delta n_1 \left(\frac{X_2}{X_1}\right) \quad (7)$$

and

$$\Gamma_1^2 = \Delta n_1 - \Delta n_2 \left(\frac{X_1}{X_2}\right) \quad (8)$$

In Figs. 3-5, values of excess binding (Γ_2^1) of different solutes per kg of protein have been plotted as function of $\left(\frac{X_2}{X_1}\right)$. From these figures it may be noted that the values of Γ_2^1 in the presence CaCl_2 and sucrose are mostly positive, so that according to eq. (3) excess water binding (Γ_1^2) in these systems are negative. Water may therefore, be said to have less affinity than these solutes towards the protein in these systems. CaCl_2 and sucrose bind to the protein in preference to water as positive excesses. In presence of other salts and urea, values of Γ_2^1 are positive for $\left(\frac{X_2}{X_1}\right)$ (equal to $\frac{m_2}{55.5}$) less than a critical bulk concentration m_2 for each system and above this concentra-

Fig. 3. Plot of Γ_2^1 , moles of solute bound per kg of hemocyanin versus $\left(\frac{X_2}{X_1}\right)$, mole ratio composition at 30 °C. (O) : LiCl, (Δ) : NaCl, (\bullet) : KCl, (\blacktriangle) : CsCl.

tion Γ_2^1 is negative. This critical bulk concentration of solute is referred to as CBC, where Γ_2^1 becomes zero. This state is also known as an “azeotropic state”, when the composition of the bulk and protein bound phase become same⁶. Values of m_2 of various solutes at the azeotropic states are presented in Table 3. For different solutes, values of m_2 are different. It thus depends on the nature of the solute in the simple system for a particular protein.

In certain regions of Γ_2^1 versus $\left(\frac{X_2}{X_1}\right)$ plots, Γ_2^1 varies linearly with $\frac{X_2}{X_1}$ so that Δn_1 and Δn_2 may be determined from the slope and the intercept of the straight line. These values are presented in Table 3 along with standard errors. In terms of the magnitudes of water binding (Δn_1) to protein, the solutes stand in the following order : $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 > \text{KCl} > \text{NaCl} > \text{KI} > \text{KBr} > \text{CsCl} > \text{CaCl}_2 > \text{sucrose} > \text{urea} > \text{LiCl}$ and the order in terms of the solute binding (Δn_2) is as follows : $\text{CaCl}_2 > \text{NaCl} > \text{KCl} > \text{urea} > \text{sucrose} > \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 > \text{CsCl} > \text{LiCl} > \text{KI} > \text{KBr}$.

Fig. 4. Plot of Γ_2^1 , moles of solute bound per kg of hemocyanin, versus $\left(\frac{X_2}{X_1}\right)$, mole ratio composition at 30 °C. (○) : KBr, (Δ) : KI, (●) : Na_2SO_4 .

The orders in terms of Δn_1 and Δn_2 do not have correlations with each other. Like other proteins^{11,12,18,22},

Fig. 5. Plot of Γ_2^1 , moles of solute bound per kg of hemocyanin, versus $\left(\frac{X_2}{X_1}\right)$, mole ratio composition at 30 °C. (○) : Sucrose, (Δ) : Urea, (●) : CaCl_2 .

these orders for different solutes are not in agreement with that to be expected from the lyotropic series. Lyotropic series in terms of Δn_1 remains qualitatively valid^{7,10,16} for BSA and egg albumin with reference to many inorganic salts. Except NaCl, KCl, KBr, KI and Na_2SO_4 , values of Δn_1 in the presence of other solutes like LiCl, CsCl, CaCl_2 , sucrose and urea are less than Δn_1^0 . Using the Gibbs-Duhem equations for single phase sample system of salt, water and protein components at isopiestic equilibrium

$$n_1^t d\mu_1 + n_2^t d\mu_2 + n_p^t d\mu_p = 0 \quad (9)$$

Table 3. Azeotropic points Δn_1 , Δn_2 and ΔG_{ws}^0 for the hydration of hemocyanin in presence of different solutes at 30 °C

Solute	m_2 At azeotropic point	Δn_1 (Moles/ kg)	Δn_2 (Moles/ kg)	$-(\Delta G_{ws}^0)$ (kJ/kg)	
				At low a_2	At high a_2
LiCl	6.82	4.76 ± 0.64	1.40 ± 0.36	35.5	14.0
NaCl	4.16	58.0 ± 3.28	4.45 ± 0.92	63.5	22.0
KCl	2.88	78.5 ± 5.96	4.10 ± 0.98	58.0	21.0
CsCl	4.60	22.7 ± 1.56	1.85 ± 0.76	62.5	9.0
KBr	0.94	42.0 ± 5.12	0.70 ± 0.21	73.0	17.0
KI	1.38	55.5 ± 6.34	1.35 ± 0.46	63.0	15.0
CaCl_2	-	17.6 ± 3.58	4.60 ± 1.38	-19.5	37.5
Na_2SO_4	1.72	81.8 ± 8.44	2.50 ± 0.32	15.5	6.0
Sucrose	-	12.8 ± 2.91	3.30 ± 0.21	46.5	29.5
Urea	8.27	10.0 ± 3.02	3.95 ± 1.80	-11.0	45.0

Whereas for reference solution at isopiestic equilibrium

$$n_1 d\mu_1 + n_2 d\mu_2 = 0 \quad (10)$$

or

$$d\mu_1 = -\frac{n_2}{n_1} d\mu_2 \quad (11)$$

Combining eqs. (9), (10) and (11)

$$\begin{aligned} -n_p d\mu_p &= (n_1^\dagger d\mu_1 + n_2^\dagger d\mu_2) \\ &= \left(n_2^\dagger - n_1^\dagger \frac{n_2}{n_1} \right) d\mu_2 = \Gamma_2^1 d\mu_2 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

It can be alternatively shown that

$$-n_p d\mu_p = -\Gamma_1^2 d\mu_1 \quad (13)$$

Since $n_p d\mu_p$ is equal to dG_p where dG_p is the free energy change per gram (or kg) of protein so that eqs. (12) and (13) can be written as

$$-\Gamma_2^1 d\mu_2 = \Gamma_1^2 d\mu_1$$

Since $n_p d\mu_p$ is equal to dG_p where dG_p is the free energy change per gram (or kg) of protein so that

$$-dG_p = \Gamma_2^1 d\mu_2 \quad (14)$$

$$= \Gamma_1^2 d\mu_1 \quad (15)$$

$$\text{Also } -(dG_p) = \Gamma_2^1 (v_+ d\mu_+ + v_- d\mu_-) \quad (15a)$$

Here μ_+ and μ_- are chemical potential of cations and anions respectively and v_+ and v_- are their stoichiometric coefficients when one molecule of electrolyte is dissociated completely in sample. Thus we can replace $d\mu_2$ in eq. (14) by $v_+ d\mu_+ + v_- d\mu_-$ so that from eq. (15) one can obtain

$$-dG_p = RT \Gamma_2^1 (v_+ + v_-) d \ln f_\pm X_\pm \quad (16)$$

f_\pm and X_\pm stand for mean activity coefficient and mean mole fraction²³ of the electrolyte whose values at given mole fraction (or molal) concentration can be calculated using appropriate tables²³.

One can now fix the appropriate equation for the standard free energy change ΔG_{ap}^0 for interaction with protein with electrolytes and water using eq. (17).

$$\Delta G_{ap}^0 = -RT(v_+ + v_-)$$

$$\left[\int_0^{X_\pm} \frac{\Gamma_2^m}{f_\pm X_\pm} d(f_\pm X_\pm) - \Gamma_2^m \ln (f_\pm X_\pm^m) \right] \quad (17)$$

Here X_\pm^m stands for the critical concentration of the electrolyte when value of Γ_2^1 hypothetically reaches the maximum and fixed value Γ_2^m .

Apparent standard free energy changes (ΔG_{ap}^0) for excess binding of different electrolytes respectively per kg of hemocyanin for changing the bulk concentration of solute from zero to unity have been calculated from graphical integration using eq. (17). For each solute, ΔG_{ap}^0 values have been plotted against $\frac{1}{\sqrt{X_\pm}}$ (vide Figs. 6 and 7)

and the extrapolated value of ΔG_{ap}^0 stands for the free energy change for the transfer of Γ_2^0 moles of solute (or Γ_1^2 mole of solvent) in excess to the bound phase of protein to change the activity of the solvent from unity to zero (or of the solute from zero to unity). Also f_\pm and X_\pm are the mean ionic activity coefficient in terms of rational mole fraction scale and mean ionic mole fraction respectively of the solute which may be evaluated using the following equations.

Fig. 6. Plot of $-\Delta G_{ap}^0$ (kJ/kg) versus $\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{a_2}} \right)$ for the hydration of hemocyanin in presence of different salts at 30 °C. (▲) : CsCl, (○) : LiCl, (Δ) : KI, (●) : KCl.

$f_{\pm} = (1 + 0.018m_2) \gamma_{\pm}$, γ_{\pm} being the mean ionic activity coefficient in terms of molality²³.

$$X_+ = \frac{v_+ m_2}{(v_+ + v_-) m_2 + 55.51};$$

$$X_- = \frac{v_- m_2}{(v_+ + v_-) m_2 + 55.51}$$
(18)

$$X_{\pm} = (X_+^{v_+} \cdot X_-^{v_-})^{1/(v_+ + v_-)}$$
(19)

The activity coefficients (f_{\pm}) for the non-electrolytic solutes like sucrose and urea are assumed to be unity and the value of ($v_+ + v_-$) is replaced by unity eq. (17) for these solutes to calculate ΔG_{ap}^0 .

Fig. 7. Plot of $-\Delta G_{ap}^0$ (kJ/kg) versus $\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{a_2}}\right)$ for the hydration of hemocyanin in presence of different salts at 30 °C. (○) : Sucrose, (●) : Na_2SO_4 , (▲) : Urea, (Δ) : CaCl_2 .

The integral part of the eq. (17) has been solved graphically between appropriate limits using the values of Γ_2^1 and $f_{\pm} X_{\pm}$ (or a_2).

In Figs. 6 and 7 values of ΔG_{ap}^0 thus calculated from the experimental data have been plotted as a function of $\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{f_{\pm} X_{\pm}}}\right)$ or $\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{a_2}}\right)$ in the presence of various solutes. From these figures it is observed that ΔG_{ap}^0 for various systems (except in the presence of CaCl_2 and urea) becomes at first negative and then increases with increase of solute activity a_2 . It means that with the increase of the solute concentration, the water binding to protein decreases.

From all these results and discussions, it may be concluded that the hydration of hemocyanin in the absence of solute is a temperature-dependent phenomenon. Various neutral salts like LiCl, NaCl, KCl, KBr, KI, CsCl, Na_2SO_4 , CaCl_2 and organic solutes like sucrose and urea have a significant role in controlling the process of hydration which may be explained in terms of Gibbs surface excess quantities (Γ_2^1 or Γ_1^2). Thermodynamic aspects of water and solute binding to hemocyanin may also be explained in terms of the change of standard Gibbs free energy (ΔG_w^0 or ΔG_{ws}^0), enthalpy (ΔH^0) and entropy (ΔS^0) which are evaluated using standard equations based on a uniform thermodynamic scale.

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